

Transportation mode recognition based on low-rate acceleration and location signals with an attention-based multiple-instance learning network

Christos Siargkas, Vasileios Papapanagiotou, Anastasios Delopoulos

Abstract—Transportation mode recognition (TMR) is a critical component of human activity recognition (HAR) that focuses on understanding and identifying how people move within transportation systems. It is commonly based on leveraging inertial, location, or both types of signals, captured by modern smartphone devices. Each type has benefits (such as increased effectiveness) and drawbacks (such as increased battery consumption) depending on the transportation mode (TM). Combining the two types is challenging as they exhibit significant differences such as very different sampling rates. This paper focuses on the TMR task and proposes an approach for combining the two types of signals in an effective and robust classifier. Our network includes two sub-networks for processing acceleration and location signals separately, using different window sizes for each signal. The two sub-networks are designed to also embed the two types of signals into the same space so that we can then apply an attention-based multiple-instance learning classifier to recognize TM. We use very low sampling rates for both signal types to reduce battery consumption. We evaluate the proposed methodology on a publicly available dataset and compare against other well known algorithms.

Index Terms—transportation mode detection, accelerometer, location, GPS, multiple instance learning, attention, hidden Markov model

I. INTRODUCTION

To discover solutions and uncover opportunities to improve the quality of life at scale in cities, it would be useful to acquire a better understanding of commuting patterns and establish new grounds of collaboration between the transportation sector and other fields of research like biomedical research [1]–[3], urban and transportation planning [4], public-policy making, environmental research [5], [6], carbon footprint analysis [7], safe driving, and journey planning. Transportation mode recognition (TMR) systems can play an integral part in this by automating the process and eliminating the need of manual data collection and annotation. Moreover, real-time recognition can

assist in identifying crucial moments and providing immediate assistance.

Given the rich arsenal of sensors available in common smartphone devices (i.e., smartphones and smartwatches), data fusion has become an integral part of TMR research, by combining multiple sensors to observe the same event from different viewpoints.

Acceleration signal can elaborately distinguish between physical activities which are characterized by volatile body movement, however, the ability to distinguish between motorized transportation modes (TMs) that are characterized by low body movement is lesser [8], [9]. In particular, when using only acceleration signal, classifiers can recognize activities such as standing still, walking, and running robustly, but exhibit significant ambiguities between car vs. bus, train vs. subway, and standing still vs. train/subway. Findings of [8] align with these limitations, highlighting the model’s constrained ability to differentiate between Subway and Train.

Contrary, location signals can capture a “higher-level” overview of the user’s movement, including distance, speed, etc; however, relying location signals requires uninterrupted interaction with satellites which is not always possible (i.e., when the user moves underground, inside a building, or along urban canyons). The inherent heterogeneity between these two sensor modalities presents an opportunity for highly-effective fusion, yet it also introduces a challenge for achieving seamless combination. Furthermore, the vastly different sampling rates used for collecting the two sensor modalities introduce another layer of complexity in robustly combining them.

In this work, we propose an intermediate-fusion deep-learning TMR model which combines two sensor modalities: acceleration and location. To address the challenges posed by variations in these two sensor modalities, including heterogeneity, distinct sampling rates, and sensor unavailability, we propose a novel model that learns independent spatio-temporal features for each modality while simultaneously mapping the heterogeneous sensor data to a shared low-dimensional embedding space. Leveraging this common embedding space, we efficiently integrate information from the diverse sensors using an attention-based multiple-instance-learning (MIL) classifier. Finally, we employ a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) for post-processing. To optimize the efficacy of MIL, we use sequences of acceleration windows instead of relying on single windows. This approach offers several advantages, such as enhancing the resolution of the acceleration input and identifying the most critical regions within the acceleration data that pertain

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to the specific TM being analyzed. We evaluate on a publicly available dataset and compare with our own implementations of other state-of-the-art algorithms.

Our main contributions are:

- We propose a novel, energy-efficient, and lightweight system for TMR that uniquely combines low sampling-rate acceleration and location signals collected by smartphone sensors, optimizing energy consumption while maintaining high effectiveness.
- We present Fusion-MIL, an attention-based MIL framework that effectively combines acceleration and location signals, overcoming challenges such as sensor heterogeneity, distinct sampling rates and sensor unavailability. We use multiple acceleration windows instead of single one, enhancing the resolution of the acceleration input and identifying regions most relevant to the final prediction. This approach inherits the interpretability of the instance-attention based MIL.
- We introduce additional processes such as data pre-processing, feature engineering, data augmentation, and pre-training to boost effectiveness.
- Extensive experimental evaluation is performed on a publicly available dataset, with a focus on cross-subject and cross-placement variability. These experiments provide in-depth insights into various factors influencing TMR, particularly the impact of device placement. Results demonstrate our method’s capability to accurately distinguish between eight different TMs in complex scenarios, surpassing the state-of-the-art methods and various alternative single-modal and multi-modal algorithms.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents an overview of recent approaches for TMR based on inertial signals, location signals, or their combination. Section III presents our proposed approach and the architecture of the artificial neural network (ANN). Section IV presents the dataset, types of experiments, and details for model training, and Section V presents the results and experimental evaluation. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Inertial and location signals offer different advantages and challenges when used for transportation mode recognition (TMR). In this section we present recent approaches for TMR from literature, organized based on their use of sensor type, with an emphasis on the requirements (i.e., sampling rate, battery consumption).

A. Location-based approaches

One of the most commonly used modalities for TMR is the location signal (i.e., geographical coordinates). In [10], James et al. explore this domain using the publicly available GeoLife Dataset [11] and process location trajectories (sampling interval of 1 to 5 sec) based on discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and deep learning techniques. In a different approach, Dabiri et al. [12] adjust all the location trajectories to a fixed length and design a CNN-based supervised travel mode identification system. This system extracts 4 features from location data,

including speed, acceleration, jerk, and bearing and identifies 5 types of TMs.

It is important to note that these studies, as well as the vast majority of the TMR studies, use the same set of users for training and testing, limiting the generalization potential to user variations such as different gait styles, walking/running patterns, speed, and travel behaviours.

In [13], location-based TMR using a random forest (RF) is combined with geographic information system (GIS) to leverage the underlying transportation network. Location is sampled only once every 15 seconds to avoid battery drain. The trained classification model is deployed to the general public, accommodating new individuals for evaluation. Authors report an average detection accuracy of 93.5% at classifying 6 TMs: car, bus, train, walking, biking and stationary. The 2021 SHL Recognition Challenge [14] also focuses on user-independent evaluation by separating participants in train and test sets (instead of separating segments of participant data). The contestant teams were provided with four radio sensor modalities, including: GPS location, GPS reception, WiFi reception, and Cell reception. These sensors were asynchronously sampled with a sampling rate of roughly 1 Hz. Sekiguchi et al. [15], using an LSTM model with location-derived features (velocity, acceleration, and angular acceleration) and XGBoost with statistical features for when location signal was not available achieved the 5th highest F1-score of 58.2%. In [16], Balabka and Shkliarenko extract 975 hand-picked features from the 4 sensors and employ an AdaNet model, provided by Google AutoML service, taking the first place with F1 score as high as 75.4%.

B. Inertial based approaches

Location signal is not always available (especially when it is derived from GPS) in shielded areas; additionally, sampling-rates can quickly drain the smartphone battery. Thus, several studies propose only inertial-based only approaches [17]. Most of them only rely on the accelerometer due to its low energy requirements and early integration into smartphones.

In [18], 3D acceleration signals are collected from 4 participants holding their phones freely in any orientation of their preference. Acceleration signal is captured at 50 Hz. After filtering and computing the signal magnitude, a CNN model discriminates between 7 TMs: stationary, walk, bicycle, car, bus, subway and train. This approach achieves an accuracy of 94.48% by splitting the data into 80% - 20% training and test sets respectively. Nonetheless, like several other studies, this study employs the same group of users for both training and testing. Contrary, Rosario et al. [19] observe that when a classifier is deployed on data of an older participant after being trained on a younger participant, its effectiveness considerably declines.

In [20], 3 common body placements are considered and acceleration is recorded both at 60 Hz and 100 Hz. A hierarchical classifier is proposed to identify 6 TMs. This approach is evaluated using a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross-validation (CV) and a leave-one-placement-out CV, achieving F1-scores of 81% and 83.3% respectively.

However, some vehicles such as automobiles and buses (or subways and trains) produce similar patterns, thus limiting the discriminative power of acceleration-only based systems [21]. To counter this, some studies propose combining multiple inertial sensor modalities.

Fang et al. [22] uses 8,311 hours of accelerometer, magnetometer, and gyroscope sensor data recorded from 224 users with a sampling rate of 30 Hz [23]. A deep neural network (DNN) is employed to recognize 5 TMs (still, walk, run, bike, and vehicle), achieving accuracy of 95%. Yet, a key challenge in TMR, especially when relying solely on inertial sensors, is the discrimination ability between similar motorized classes [24], [25].

In Zhao et al. [26], a Bi-LSTM model is trained on accelerometer and gyroscope data, sampled at 50 Hz, to detect 6 TMs: still, walk, run, bike, bus, subway. The model is trained on data from 8 users and is evaluated on 3 separate users, achieving an overall accuracy of 92.8%. However, all data is collected from smartphones with a fixed orientation and placement, limiting generalization to other body positions. In fact, according to [27], [28], inertial data may differ significantly across different body positions. In [8], Tang et al. use a deep multimodal fusion network on accelerometer, magnetometer, and gyroscope data sampled at 20 Hz and segmented into 60-second windows. Their proposed method achieves a remarkable accuracy of 95.1% and an F1-score of 94.7% in detecting eight different transportation modes.

The 2018 SHL recognition challenge [29] focuses on time-invariant evaluation using 62 days (272 hours) as training data and the remaining 20 days (95 hours) as test data, while providing the participant teams with 7 different motion-sensor modalities. Ito et al. [30] apply a deep CNN to two-dimensional spectrogram images extracted from the sensor sequences, taking the third place with F1-score 88.8%. In the position-independent 2019 SHL recognition challenge [31], Choi and Lee [32] achieve the second highest F1-score 75.9% by introducing a deep multi-modal fusion model named EmbraceNet that combines multiple inertial sensor modalities which are independently pre-processed by a CNN.

C. Hybrid approaches

Compared to inertial sensors, location sensors can offer a “higher” overview of the user’s movement, thus serving as a complementary data source when used alongside inertial sensors. Moreover, location sensors are mostly position invariant and can be effectively combined with inertial sensors to minimize the impact of the varying smartphone placement and orientation. Consequently, a combination of location and inertial sensor modalities can enhance the robustness of a TMR system and improve its discrimination abilities. In fact, according to Wang et al. [9], the combination of location and accelerometer outperforms the combination of three inertial sensor modalities (accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer), while the combination of all four modalities only improves the recognition effectiveness slightly. Additionally, [9] also emphasize that the combination of location and acceleration signals remarkably improves the recognition accuracy for each class compared to

relying solely on accelerometer data. Notably, the accuracy of distinguishing between Car and Bus, as well as between Train and Subway, shows significant improvement with the combined use of location and accelerometer data which is what we propose in this work.

In [33], Reddy et al. introduces a hybrid approach using both location and acceleration data captured from 6 different smartphones (worn in 6 different body positions) by 16 participants. Each smartphone contains an accelerometer that can sample at 32 Hz and a built-in GPS receiver that can sample at 1 Hz. The proposed classifier consists of a DT followed by a discrete hidden Markov model (HMM) and recognizes 5 TMs: still, walk, run, bicycle, motorized. The classifier is evaluated with LOSO CV, achieving an average and a minimum accuracy of 93.6% and 88.2% respectively. However, this method can’t handle location-signal loss.

In [34], location (GPS) trajectories are resampled evenly with a frequency of 1 Hz and the accelerometer readings are resampled to a frequency of 50 Hz. The proposed approach copes with location signal loss by including positioning data obtained from the cell network and relying solely on accelerometer features when the trajectory cannot be reconstructed with sufficient accuracy. A randomized ensemble of classifiers with an HMM is proposed to differentiate among 8 different TMs: bus, car, bike, tram, train, subway, walk, and motorcycle. Two experiments are presented: a 4-class task (walk, car, bus, bike) where the classifier achieves a high recall accuracy of 91%, and a 5-class task (walk, car, bus, subway, train) where classification effectiveness is degraded (recall accuracy of 76%).

In [35], Priscoli et al. use accelerometer (50 Hz), gyroscope (50 Hz), and location (1 Hz) signals to recognize seven TMs: walk, car, motorbike, tram, still, bus, and subway. This is the only work, in our knowledge, that proposes a deep learning TMR system based on hybrid information from both location and inertial sensor modalities. Specifically, recursive neural networks (RNNs) with statistical features achieve the second best effectiveness (88%), while a CNN model with 3D acceleration, 3D gyroscope, and speed achieves 98.6% without any pre-processing.

In [36], location, accelerometer, and heart rate data are collected from 126 individuals over a period of 7 days. Random Forest (RF) algorithms are used to perform TMR on a minute-by-minute basis. This study focuses on the participant-level split and the proposed method demonstrates varying prediction rates, achieving a prediction rate of 95% for biking, 65% for public transport, and an overall prediction rate of 90%. Notably, this study, like the vast majority of hybrid studies, use early fusion to combine these sensor modalities by either extracting statistical features or concatenating the raw signals.

To date, most approaches use location and inertial sensor data collected at high sampling rates; in most studies, location sampling rate falls within the range of 1 to 5 seconds [37], [38], while the sampling rate of inertial data ranges between 20 and 30 Hz [39]. Such requirements tend to have a strong impact on modern smartphones energy consumption. Some studies have suggested that inertial sensors sampled at 20

Hz can sufficiently discriminate between various TMs [40] and a sampling rate of 10 Hz is adequate for distinguishing between different mobility patterns [41]. Notably, one study demonstrated that reducing the sampling rate from 100 Hz to 12.5 Hz led to a threefold increase in the duration of data collection on a single battery charge [42]. Regarding location data, power consumption decreases with increased sampling time and it is estimated that employing a sampling time of 40 seconds can, on average, extend the mobile phone battery life by 25.4% compared to the standard sampling setting of 1 Hz [43].

Thus, one challenge in developing such a hybrid approach is to fuse the different sensor modalities efficiently and maintain low sampling-rate requirements. To address these challenges, we use accelerometer signals at 10 Hz and location signals at 1/60 Hz (one sample per minute) and propose a hybrid attention-based MIL system that extracts instance-level embeddings through single-sensor-based feature encoders and fuses the instance-level features into joint representations through a deep MIL mechanism [44]. The network’s ability of being selective enables it to effectively fuse the acceleration and location modalities, adeptly addressing situations where location signal is not available by solely relying on accelerometer data. Moreover, the network’s interpretability capabilities offer a rich spectrum of insights into the TMR task. The classification task includes eight TMs: still, walk, run, bike, car, bus, train, and subway, and the model is evaluated with LOSO CV, achieving accuracy and F1-Score of 90.8% and 92.6%, respectively.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our approach is based on an artificial neural network (ANN) that separately processes windows of acceleration and location signal and then combines them with MIL. Each signal type is originally pre-processed and then windows are extracted. We use two different sub-networks for extracting features from each signal type and then map them to a common embedding feature space. A third sub-network is then used that performs attention-based MIL. Finally, we post-process the predicted labels using an HMM.

A. Acceleration pre-processing

While it is possible to use high sampling rates to capture acceleration in modern devices, continuous capturing at such rates can have a detrimental effect on battery life. Thus, we opt to sample acceleration at a low rate of $f_s^a = 10$ Hz. We extract consecutive windows of $T^a = 60$ sec. This choice is based on the assumption that TM does not change significantly within a single minute. Experimenting with the dataset also shows similar results (see Section V-B1).

The accelerometer provides 3D measurements: $\mathbf{a}[n] = [a_x[n], a_y[n], a_z[n]]^T$. To remove the effect of phone and sensor orientation, we compute the magnitude $a[n] = \|\mathbf{a}[n]\|$ [45]. We also compute the magnitude of jerk as:

$$j[n] = \|\mathbf{a}[n] - \mathbf{a}[n-1]\| \cdot f_s^a \quad (1)$$

because it is orientation-independent and reflects body-related accelerations [46]. Thus, we obtain a signal of 2 channels: $[a[n], j[n]]^T$.

It is important to note that we do not remove the gravity component from the magnitude $a[n]$, as it proves to be a source of valuable information (based on early-stage experimentations with the dataset). However, the effect of gravity is indirectly removed when computing jerk, $j[n]$. Thus, our method takes advantage of both versions of the signal.

Finally, we transform each of the 2 channels into spectrograms, using the short-time Fourier transform (STFT). Power spectrum is estimated in 10-second segments with 9 sec overlap, yielding 51 segments in total. We rescale the power spectrum bands into 51 bands by grouping frequencies; each band has double bandwidth compared to the previous one, i.e.:

$$\frac{f_b[i+1] - f_b[i]}{f_b[i] - f_b[i-1]} = 2, \quad i = 1, \dots, 50 \quad (2)$$

where $f_b[i-1]$ and $f_b[i]$ are the lowest and highest frequency of the i -th band. The spectrograms are then concatenated as two channels, resulting in a single “image” of $51 \times 51 \times 2$.

To reduce the risk of overfitting, particularly in cases when there is a considerable overlap between training samples, and to enhance the generalization capabilities of our ANN, we incorporate data augmentation. Typically, accelerometer signals are augmented using signal processing transformations such as jittering, scaling, rotation, and permutation [47], [48]. While these methods have shown improvements in recognition rates, they tend to disregard the correlations between signals, limiting the potential to uncover cross-signal features. We adopt an alternative augmentation policy, proposed by Park [49]. Inspired by cut-out [50], consecutive time steps or frequency channels within the spectrogram are randomly masked, reducing reliance on specific regions or features while preserving the intrinsic cross-signal correlations. In particular, we randomly choose 0, 1, or 2 frequency bands of random width (0 to 5 rows), and also randomly choose 0, 1, or 2 time intervals of random length (0 to 5 columns), and mask them.

B. Location pre-processing

Most studies use location data captured at high sampling rates (e.g. 1 Hz). Such rates have a notable impact on battery usage, even in modern smartphones. Thus, we opt for a reduced sampling rate of $f_s^l = 1/60$ Hz, which translates to one sample per minute, in order to simulate a more battery-friendly data collection approach.

Capturing location data depends on GPS signal availability, resulting in certain sections of the time-series data being frequently absent due to poor satellite reception. We identify two types of “gaps”: (a) brief signal losses, lasting less than 3 minutes, for which we employ linear interpolation to estimate the missing values, and (b) extended periods of signal loss, exceeding 3 minutes, during which we apply a masking value the missing values that signifies the presence of missing data. This approach is necessary since linear interpolation would yield erroneous data in such cases.

The signal is then segmented to windows, similarly to the accelerometer signal. However, we use windows of 12 minutes. This value of 12 minutes enables us to capture behavior that is not observable in shorter durations (i.e., moving through heavy traffic in a motor vehicle can create patterns that last longer than 1 minute). It should be also noted that choosing smaller window sizes (such as 1 minute as in the case of the acceleration signal) would yield windows with very few signal samples (e.e., only one for 1-minute windows).

The big difference in window lengths between the two modalities as well as the orders of magnitude of difference between the sampling rates creates a challenge when trying to combine them in a single detector. We face this challenge by designing our architecture appropriately (please see Section III-C for more details).

Using raw location coordinates as input data is not practical as it may lead to the development of a location-dependent classifier. To overcome this we transform the coordinates into location-invariant features. Specifically, for a window of location signal, $l[n] = (\text{lat}[n], \text{lon}[n])$, at timestamps $t[n]$ for $n = 0, \dots, 11$, we consider 2 features, namely speed as:

$$v^l[n] = \frac{d(l[n], l[n-1])}{t[n] - t[n-1]} \quad (3)$$

and acceleration as:

$$a^l[n] = \frac{v^l[n] - v^l[n-1]}{t[n] - t[n-1]} \quad (4)$$

where $d(\bullet, \bullet)$ is the Haversine distance between two pairs of coordinates. Because of how v^l and a^l are computed, the result is a 10×2 matrix. Additionally, we calculate 5 more features for each window: mean and standard deviation of speed, mean and standard deviation of speed derivative, and ‘‘movability’’ [51]. Movability indicates the ratio of total displacement to the total distance covered within the examined period:

$$m = \frac{d(l[11], l[0])}{\sum_{k=1}^{11} d(l[k], l[k-1])} \quad (5)$$

C. Embedding signals into a common space

To effectively integrate the information from the two sensor modalities into a cohesive joint representation, we must account for the variations between these modal inputs, including their distinct nature, representation, sampling rate, and window size. To tackle these challenges we adopt a two-pronged approach, employing two parallel modality-specific branches to embed the information originating from acceleration and location into a common, embedding space. To achieve this, we project the data of Sections III-A and III-B onto \mathbb{R}^d (where $d = 256$ in our case), using two feature encoders:

- $\mathbf{f}_a : \mathbb{R}^{51 \times 51 \times 2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, the acceleration-feature encoder
- $\mathbf{f}_l : \mathbb{R}^{10 \times 2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, the location-feature encoder

It is important to note that we have designed the two modality-specific networks so that their output is the same, i.e., both produce vectors in \mathbb{R}^d where $d = 256$. Thus, windows of both signal types are embedded in the same feature space, enabling the application of MIL.

Fig. 1. Visual representation of the windows that are used for a single bag (for MIL). Given a target timestamp (dashed line), we include $n_l = 1$ window of location data that is 12 minutes long and $n_a = 3$ successive windows of acceleration data that are each 1 minute long. The next bag is obtained by shifting everything by 1 minute.

Thus, we create bags of $n = 4$ instances, including $n_a = 3$ acceleration windows and $n_l = 1$ location windows, as shown in Figure 1. This, combined with MIL, enables us to fuse the two types of signals despite their very different nature.

The acceleration-feature encoder, \mathbf{f}_a , is a convolution model. It consists of an initial batch-normalization layer, followed by 3 convolutional blocks, and then 2 fully-connected (FC) blocks. Each convolutional block consists of a 2D-convolutional layer with 3×3 kernels, batch normalization, Re.L.U. activation, and finally max-pooling (ratio 2 : 1 per dimension and stride of 2). The 3 convolutional blocks have 16, 32, and 64 filters respectively. A FC block consists of a dropout layer, a FC layer, batch normalization, and Re.L.U. activation. The first block acts as a bottleneck, by decreasing the dimension to 128. The second block increases the dimension to d .

The location-feature encoder, \mathbf{f}_l , combines a bi-directional LSTM of 128 cells with the set of hand-crafted features (Section III-B) with 3 FC blocks. Prior to the Bi-LSTM layer, batch normalization is applied. The output of the Bi-LSTM layer, which includes both the first and last states of the Bi-LSTM, is concatenated with 5 hand-crafted features that are computed during the feature extraction phase. Three fully-connected blocks follow; each block consists of a fully-connected layer, batch normalization, and then Re.L.U. activation.

D. Multiple instance learning and classification

Our main focus is leveraging MIL to effectively integrate information from the two types of modalities. We use bags of n instances, including n_a acceleration instances and n_l location instances, as shown in Figure 1. However, directly combining acceleration and location instances in their raw form is not a feasible solution due to their inherent differences, such as different representation and captured information. To address this challenge, we map them into a common embedding space, as discussed in Section III-C. The acceleration feature encoder \mathbf{f}_a transforms the acceleration instances $S_a = \{\mathbf{s}_{a,1}, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{a,n_a}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times 51 \times 51 \times 2}$ into a set of acceleration-based embeddings $H_a = \{\mathbf{h}_{a,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{a,n_a}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times d}$. Similarly, the location feature encoder transforms the location instances $S_l = \{\mathbf{s}_{l,1}, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{l,n_l}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times 10 \times 2}$ into a set of location-based embeddings $H_l = \{\mathbf{h}_{l,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{l,n_l}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times d}$.

Subsequently, we introduce the MIL ANN $\mathbf{f} : \mathbb{R}^{N \times d} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, which aggregates the multi-modal instance-level embeddings $H = \{\mathbf{h}_{a,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{a,n_a}, \mathbf{h}_{l,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{l,n_l}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$ into a fused encoding of the same dimension $d = 256$.

Fig. 2. Proposed multi-modal TMR network. The input is a bag containing two types of instances: acceleration (n_a) and location (n_l). Instances are processed in parallel by two modality-specific feature encoders f_a and f_l accordingly, which embed them in the same d -dimensional space. The attention-based MIL ANN f , follows; it aggregates n instances (of the \mathbb{R}^d embedding space) into a fused attentive encoding of the same dimension d . Finally, to make transportation mode predictions, a small classification network maps the fused encoding \mathbf{z} into category-wise decision scores.

To emphasize the expressiveness of each instance and prioritize the most useful ones, we propose a weighted average of the instance-level embeddings. Inspired by the work of Ilse [44] as well as of Papadopoulos [52], we design an attention-based fusion network responsible for determining the instance weights a_n for the embedded instances \mathbf{h}_n . This network can be formalized as follows:

$$a_n = \frac{e^{(\mathbf{w}^T \tanh(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{h}_n^T) \odot \text{sigm}(\mathbf{U}\mathbf{h}_n^T))}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{(\mathbf{w}^T \tanh(\mathbf{V}\mathbf{h}_j^T) \odot \text{sigm}(\mathbf{U}\mathbf{h}_j^T))}} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 1}$, $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times d}$, and $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times d}$ are trainable parameters of the attention network, and \odot is the Hadamard product operator. Accordingly, the contribution of the individual instances is subject to the attention weights $\{a_{a,1}, \dots, a_{a,n_a}, a_{l,1}, \dots, a_{l,n_l}\}$. By definition, it always holds that $\sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_{a,i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} a_{l,i} = 1$, where the first term indicates the importance attributed to the acceleration modality, while the second term represents the importance of the location modality. Consequently, a modal-fused encoding \mathbf{z} is derived by calculating the weighted sum of the instance-level embeddings as:

$$\mathbf{z} = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n \cdot \mathbf{h}_n = \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_{a,i} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{a,i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} a_{l,i} \cdot \mathbf{h}_{l,i} \quad (7)$$

Finally, the classification ANN, $\mathbf{c} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, maps the fused attentive encoding $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ to the label space (where $m = 8$ in our case); It is a small network, consisting of one fully-connected block (FC layer, batch normalization, and Re.L.U. activation) followed by one FC layer. The problem at hand is formulated as a multi-class classification task, in the sense that there is always a single “right” mode to be recognized. However, given that certain transportation modes, like “train” and “walking”, are not mutually exclusive, the sigmoid activation is employed to provide the final class probability of the j -th TM p_j (out of 8 TMs). A complete overview of the entire architecture is shown in Figure 2.

E. Post-processing

While our ANN classifies each example (bag) independently, it is worth noting that there are correlations in transportation mode patterns. For instance, it is unlikely that we would immediately take the bus after riding the subway, without walking in between. To account for such correlations and improve the accuracy of the classification output, a common approach is to apply a smoothing operation, such as a rolling median filter. In our work we employ an HMM that effectively captures temporal dependencies inherent in transportation mode patterns to determine the most probable sequence of classifications and to mitigate classification noise. We apply the HMM in the following manner:

- States are defined as the TMs, i.e., a total of 8 states are defined
- State-transition probabilities $P(c_m|c_{m-1})$ are estimated from the transition matrix derived from the combined training and validation sets
- Emission probabilities $P(c_m|\hat{c}_m)$ are estimated using the prediction probability estimates p
- Start probabilities $P(c_1)$ are uniformly set to $1/8$ (since 8 is the number of TM classes)
- The HMM is applied to each recording session and the most likely sequence of predictions is computed

IV. EXPERIMENTATION SETUP

A. Dataset

To evaluate our approach we employ the publicly available “SHL Preview Dataset”. This dataset is available as part of the complete Sussex-Huawei Locomotion Dataset [9], [53] and includes 59 hours of annotated recordings; it was captured using 4 different smartphones (attached in 4 different body positions) on 3 participants, as they went about their normal lives over the course of 3 days. This dataset contain 8 TMs: still, walk, run, bike, car, bus, train, and subway, and preserves all sensor modalities except for audio. In our study, we only consider the accelerometer and location sensor modalities. Acceleration signals are downsampled from the original 100

Hz to 10 Hz and location signals are downsampled from 1 Hz to 1/60 Hz. The processed acceleration signals are segmented into discrete frames, each with 600 samples (60 sec). At this sample rate, the dataset yields a total of 3,421 acceleration frames, resulting in a total data size of $3,421 \times 600$ for each sensor placement. The transportation mode labels are synchronized with the acceleration frames, yielding a total of 3,421 labels. Location signals are segmented into 12-minute windows, each containing 12 samples with an 11-minute overlap with neighboring windows. Location data is recorded asynchronously with average availability of location signal of 80%. In total, 2,715 location samples are obtained against the overall 3,421 acceleration frames and labels.

In our scenario, we divide the dataset using LOSO; each user’s data is used in turn for testing and the data from the remaining users are used for model development. The development data (for each LOSO iteration) consist of data from 2 participants. We split into 80% training set and 20% validation set using a stratified split framework [54] so that both sets maintain the same label and user distribution.

However, random splitting may produce heavily dependent sets since pairs of highly correlated neighboring windows could be assigned to the training and validation set respectively [55]. To avoid this, we select long, continuous streams of data (instead of individual windows) as the unit for random splitting. It is important to note that, since both training and validation data are captured from the same subjects, effectiveness on the validation set may be positively biased compared to the expected effectiveness on the unseen test set.

B. Model Training

While our proposed ANN (Figure 2) can be trained end-to-end, we opt to separately train the acceleration-feature encoder f_a . Subsequently, we freeze the trained weights and integrate them in the complete ANN model and train it, as described in Section V-C2. Both training steps are implemented in the same manner. A standard categorical cross-entropy (CCE) is used as the loss function to compute the error between the prediction probabilities and the true labels. To minimize the CCE loss and update the trainable weights, the Adam optimizer [56] is used with an initial learning rate of 10^{-4} . We use a batch size of 32 and train for at most 80 epochs. To avoid overfitting we use early stopping to identify the ideal number of epochs for training the network.

V. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

We evaluate effectiveness on the basis of accuracy and macro-averaged F1-score. All subsequent experiments are conducted in a user-independent manner (using LOSO). We also repeat each experiment 15 times to account for random initialization of model weights and random train and validation set split.

A. Influence of device placement

To assess the effectiveness of our model and gain insights into the influence of device placement, we propose a comprehensive assessment from three different perspectives:

TABLE I
RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH ON THE EIGHT-CLASS TASK.
RESULTS ARE AVERAGES ACROSS 15 RUNS.

	No HMM		HMM	
	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score
<i>Per-placement</i>				
Bag	88.0	84.9	91.5	87.3
Hand	82.0	81.3	87.7	85.6
Hips	85.5	80.3	88.7	82.0
Torso	84.9	79.4	88.4	83.3
Average	85.1	81.5	89.1	84.6
<i>All-placements</i>				
Bag	90.5	89.0	94.6	92.6
Hand	84.8	84.5	90.3	89.5
Hips	89.1	87.8	93.0	91.2
Torso	88.2	85.4	92.5	89.7
Average	88.1	86.7	92.6	90.8
<i>Mixed-placement</i>				
One	86.6	84.8	91.3	88.6
Multiple	89.3	87.9	93.7	92.3

- *Per-placement*: we exclusively train and test our model using accelerometer data obtained from a single smartphone position
- *All-placements*: we train our model using data from all four distinct acceleration data streams, each corresponding to a different recording position. Subsequently, we evaluate the model’s effectiveness using accelerometer data obtained exclusively from a single position
- *Mixed-placement*: we generate new virtual streams by combining sequential acceleration data randomly obtained from different positions. This experiment aims to simulate real-world scenarios where the position of the smartphone changes over time. We conduct two experiments of this type; one utilizing a single mixed stream for training and another utilizing multiple mixed streams (four in total) for training. We include both experiments for a more thorough evaluation

It is important to note that we do not include any information regarding the placement of the acceleration sensor in any of the experiments mentioned above. Instead, the model remains unbiased and agnostic towards sensor placement, enabling independent learning and distinguishing of the sources of the acceleration data. Furthermore, these experiments are specifically focused on the accelerometer sensors. In contrast, location signals exhibit minimal to no variation across different recording positions. This suggests that the inclusion of location signal in the recognition system enhances its robustness to variations in position.

Based on Table I there is a clear ranking of sensor placement: Bag > Hips > Torso > Hand. The data collected from the Hand placement appears to be noisier compared to the other three placements. This is likely due to the physical contact and interaction between the hand and the phone, as it introduces more variability and interference in the captured data. Additionally, the Hand placement seems to be more sensitive to individual user variations and the way each subject

uses their smartphone. On the contrary, placing the phone in a Bag yields higher inference accuracy since this placement involves less movement variability and is in close proximity to the body. Hips and Torso exhibit similar behavior.

Table I also demonstrates a significant improvement in effectiveness for the generalized classifier when compared to the per-placement experiment. Evidently, in the second experiment, the model is trained across different placements, thus learning more general features, while reducing the risk of overfitting the data from a specific placement.

One might expect the effectiveness in the mixed-placement experiment to be on par with the average effectiveness of the all-placements experiment, since both experiments utilize all the available data from every recording placement. However, our model can benefit from the mixed streams and the dynamic smartphone position; the attention-based MIL mechanism can effectively allocate its attention among a sequence of acceleration windows obtained from different positions and leverage the changing position in its advantage (see Section V-D). For instance, if a sequence contains two windows obtained from the Hand position and one obtained from the Bag position, the model will likely prioritize the window acquired from the Bag position. This increase in effectiveness is evident on Table I.

B. Acceleration-specific study

In all subsequent studies, we maintain the structure of the second experiment (as mentioned in V-A), and the effectiveness is reported as the average score across all testing positions. To gain insights into the acceleration-specific aspect of our proposed model, we examine the impact of three important components: the pre-processing pipeline, using MIL to exploit acceleration data, and the importance of data augmentation.

1) *Pre-processing pipeline*: Initially, we conduct tests using various sampling frequencies and the findings indicate that the highest accuracy is attained at a sampling rate of 10 Hz. We, then, explore the importance of the acceleration-derived signals, comparing all potential axes $\mathbf{a}[n] = [a_x[n], a_y[n], a_z[n]]^T$, along with the magnitude $a[n]$ and the jerk norm $j[n]$. Individually, the magnitude outperforms all other signals, while the jerk exhibits the poorest effectiveness. However, when combined, the magnitude and jerk yield better results compared to using the magnitude alone, and slightly worst to utilizing all the signals together. Next, we compare the different parameters involved in generating the 2D spectrogram representations. We observe that employing the logarithm of the power yields superior results compared to using the raw power. Additionally, a logarithmic interpolation for the frequency axis proves to be an effective approach for reducing data size while retaining essential information. Finally, after experimenting with different short-time Fourier transform (STFT) window durations, we conclude that the highest effectiveness is achieved for a window with a duration of 10 seconds.

2) *MIL for acceleration*: In this study, we employ MIL to leverage sequences of acceleration windows, instead of relying solely on individual acceleration windows.

To assess the importance of this method, we compare three variations of our model:

Fig. 3. Accuracy comparison between Acc-CNN, Acc-MIL and Fusion-MIL versus the duration d of acceleration input data

- **Acc-CNN**: A single d -minute acceleration window is fed into Acc-CNN. This network consists of the acceleration-feature encoder f_a (see Section III-C) followed by a classification layer (FC layer and sigmoid activation) that maps the final embedding \mathbf{h}_a into class probabilities p .
- **Acc-MIL**: The same d -minute window is now segmented into a sequence of d successive one-minute windows, which are fed to Acc-MIL. Similar to Acc-CNN, Acc-MIL also includes the acceleration-feature encoder f_a but additionally incorporates the MIL ANN f , followed by the same classification layer.
- **Fusion-MIL**: A sequence of d one-minute acceleration windows along with a single 12-minute location window, as depicted in Figure 1. The proposed Fusion-MIL model exploits this bag of multi-modal instances to perform TMR, as illustrated in Figure 2

In Figure 3, we present a effectiveness comparison between these three approaches as the duration d of the input increases. Evidently, removing MIL causes a clear effectiveness drop.

3) *Data augmentation*: As we progressively increase the number of acceleration instances, we inadvertently increase the overlap across different examples, increasing the risk of over-fitting. To mitigate this issue and improve generalization, we opt to augment the acceleration data before feeding it into the model (see section III-A). Figure V-B3 investigates the influence of data augmentation on the effectiveness of Acc-MIL as the number of acceleration instances increases.

C. Multi-modal study

We assess the effect of three significant designs, i.e. alternative approaches to Fusion-MIL, pre-training, and Markov smoothing.

1) *Comparison with alternative approaches*: We compare the classification effectiveness of our proposed Fusion-MIL model to the following single-modal and multi-modal approaches (results in Table II):

- **Loc-LSTM**: A location-only ANN with a 12-minute location window as its input. This network consists of the location-feature encoder f_l followed by a classification layer (FC layer and sigmoid activation) that maps the final embedding \mathbf{h}_l into class probabilities p .

Fig. 4. Effect of data augmentation on the accuracy of Acc-MIL versus the number d of one-minute acceleration instances

TABLE II
EFFECTIVENESS COMPARISON WITH ALTERNATIVE SINGLE-MODAL (SM)
AND MULTI-MODAL (MM) METHODS

Method	Accuracy	F1-score
<i>without MIL</i>		
Loc-LSTM (SM)	72.3	61.4
Acc-CNN (SM)	81.2	80.7
Fusion-Concat (MM)	84.5	81.3
<i>with MIL</i>		
Acc-MIL (SM)	82.5	81.9
Fusion-Concat++ (MM)	85.2	82.5
Fusion-MIL (MM)	86.1	84.1

- Acc-CNN: A acceleration-only ANN with a 3-minute acceleration window as its input (see Section V-B2).
- Fusion-Concat: A multi-modal network that accepts a 3-minute acceleration window and a 12-minute location window as a paired input. It combines the acceleration-feature encoder f_a and the location-feature encoder f_l , followed by a fusion layer that concatenates the 256-dimensional modal embeddings h_a and h_l . The modal-fused 512-dimensional encoding z , is fed to the classification ANN c to derive the final classification probabilities.
- Acc-MIL: A acceleration-only ANN that uses MIL to leverage a bag of $n_a = 3$ successive one-minute acceleration windows for classification (see V-B2).
- Fusion-Concat++: We enhance Fusion-Concat, by substituting its original f_a sub-network with Acc-MIL. The Acc-MIL branch exploits a set of $n_a = 3$ successive one-minute acceleration windows, mapping them into a joint 256-dimensional embedding h_a , while the f_l branch maps a 12-minute location window into a 256-dimensional embedding h_l . The 2 embeddings are fused through the concatenation layer and the resulting modal-fused encoding z is mapped to the label space.

2) *Pre-training*: Training the proposed ANN end-to-end reduces effectiveness, primarily due to the limited availability of paired acceleration-location data in comparison to the available acceleration-only data (the same location recording corresponds to 4 different accelerometer recordings from 4

TABLE III
EFFECT OF PRE-TRAINING

Encoder pre-training	Accuracy	F1-score
No pre-training	86.1	84.1
Location encoder f_l	87.0	84.8
Acceleration encoder f_a	88.1	86.7
Both encoders f_a & f_l	88.8	87.4

TABLE IV
OVERALL EFFECTIVENESS OF OUR PROPOSED METHOD. AVERAGES AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS ARE COMPUTED OVER THE 4 PLACEMENTS AND FOR EACH PLACEMENT WE PERFORM 15 RUNS WITH RANDOM INITIAL MODEL WEIGHTS AND TRAIN/VALIDATION SPLIT.

	Accuracy	F1-score	Precision	Recall
no HMM	88.1 \pm 0.7	86.7 \pm 1.0	87.8 \pm 0.8	86.6 \pm 1.2
HMM	92.6 \pm 1.0	90.8 \pm 1.5	92.8 \pm 1.0	90.6 \pm 1.6

different smartphone positions). Thus, we opt to separately pre-train the uni-modal feature encoders and then use the trained weights in the full ANN model:

- Acceleration encoder pre-training: To train f_a we adopt the Acc-CNN framework (Section V-B2) with 1-minute acceleration windows. After training f_a with all available training acceleration data we discard the classification layer and train the multi-modal ANN. We randomly use only one acceleration-location pair (out of 4) per instance. To prevent over-fitting, we freeze the trained weights of f_a and solely train the remaining layers. This approach uses all available data and reduces the risk of overfitting.
- Location encoder pre-training: We pre-train f_l following a similar process; we include this baseline for a more comprehensive evaluation.
- Both encoders pre-training: We pre-train both acceleration and location feature encoders.

Table III provides a comparison of incorporating pre-trained uni-modal encoders. The results clearly indicate that the acceleration pre-trained model surpasses the no pre-training model. By pre-training both encoders there is only a marginal effectiveness improvement compared to solely pre-training the acceleration encoder.

3) *Smoothing with HMMs*: To determine the most probable sequence of TMs we employ Markov smoothing, which reduces classification noise by exploiting the temporal correlation between neighbouring samples. The HMM uses the prediction probability estimates (p) as emission probabilities $P(c_m|\hat{c}_m)$ while the transition probabilities $P(c_m|c_{m-1})$ are estimated using the combined training and validation sets. Table IV presents the effect of applying HMM smoothing and Figure 5 shows the ROC curve without the HMM. It can be observed that the area under the curve is highest for non-motorized TMs (still, walk, run and bike) and slightly lower for motorized modes of transportation.

D. Model interpretability

The significance of individual instances is determined by their respective attention weights, i.e.:

Fig. 5. Multi-class ROC curves for Fusion-MIL

TABLE V
MEAN ATTENTION WEIGHT STD. PER ACCELERATION BAG

TM	Weight Std.
Still	0.041
Walk	0.034
Run	0.026
Bike	0.042
Car	0.058
Bus	0.058
Train	0.058
Subway	0.078

$\{a_{a,1}, \dots, a_{a,n_a}, a_{l,1}, \dots, a_{l,n_l}\}$. These attention weights play a crucial role in determining the contribution of each instance within the model and enable the interpretability of our multi-modal model.

Using MIL on sequences of acceleration windows improves interpretability, enhances the resolution of the acceleration input, and enables the identification of the most relevant regions in the acceleration signal for the final prediction.

Table V presents the average standard deviation of attention weights $\{a_{a,1}, \dots, a_{a,n_a}\}$ per class. This analysis enables us to assess whether the MIL ANN evenly allocates its attention across all acceleration instances within a bag or not. For periodic activities, such as “walking” or “running”, we anticipate the generation of repetitive acceleration recordings and similar instance-level embeddings $\{\mathbf{h}_{a,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{a,n_a}\}$. Accordingly, we would expect uniformly distributed attention weights $\{a_{a,1}, \dots, a_{a,n_a}\}$, resulting in low standard deviation, as verified in Table V. On the contrary, transportation modes like “car” or “bus” are expected to produce dissimilar instances (such as a “stopped” instance followed by one “moving” instance), resulting in diverging attention weights and high standard deviation, as verified in Table V. Basically, in such cases, sorting the acceleration instances by their attention weights helps select the most “active” recordings for further examination.

Table VI presents the average position weights per class, providing insight on how the MIL ANN allocates its attention among acceleration instances in accordance to their recording

TABLE VI
MEAN ATTENTION WEIGHT PER PLACEMENT

TM	Torso	Hips	Bag	Hand
Still	0.260	0.244	0.253	0.243
Walk	0.278	0.236	0.263	0.223
Run	0.256	0.250	0.251	0.242
Bike	0.257	0.245	0.257	0.241
Car	0.256	0.253	0.262	0.229
Bus	0.255	0.253	0.258	0.235
Train	0.254	0.252	0.266	0.228
Subway	0.260	0.255	0.262	0.223
Average	0.259	0.249	0.259	0.233

TABLE VII
MEAN MODALITY ATTENTION WEIGHT

Mode	Modality	
	Location	Acceleration
Still	0.355	0.645
Walk	0.384	0.616
Run	0.422	0.578
Bike	0.454	0.546
Car	0.461	0.539
Bus	0.426	0.574
Train	0.468	0.532
Subway	0.190	0.810

positions. To obtain these findings, we use the structure of the third experiment, which involves mixed streams of acceleration recordings. This allows us to examine how the model responds to bags composed of successive acceleration instances recorded in various body positions.

As mentioned in Section III-D, $\sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_{a,i}$ indicates the weight attributed to the acceleration modality, while $\sum_{i=1}^{n_l} a_{l,i}$ indicates the weight attributed to the location modality. Table VII presents the average modality weights per class to provide insights on which modality the model relies the most when recognizing particular TMs.

E. Comparison against literature

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, our system is compared with prior works employing both traditional machine learning techniques and deep learning methods (Table VIII provides a concise summary of these studies). To ensure comparability, we replicate the approaches outlined in the original papers, applying them to the SHL preview Dataset and evaluating their effectiveness through our experiments. In Table IX, we present the accuracy and F1-score results of our method against state-of-the-art approaches, with and without the inclusion of the post-processing step (Hidden Markov Model). Additionally, we provide the standard deviation across different sensor placements alongside the scores.

Reddy et al.’s approach [33] achieves an accuracy of 90.1% in the all-placements experiment. Consistent with their work, we modify the classification task by reducing the number of distinct classes to 5, merging all 4 motorized modes into a single class. Their proposed fusion model incorporates DTs and an HMM with acceleration signals at 32 Hz and location at 1 Hz segmented into 1-second windows. While our findings

TABLE VIII
SUMMARY OF WORKS USING INERTIAL AND LOCATION DATA TO DETECT TRANSPORTATION MODES

	acc.	gyr.	mag.	loc.	Input	Sampling rate	Params (10^6)	Num. TMs	Reported F1-Score
CNN1D [18]	✓				raw data	50 Hz	0.3	7	94.5
CNN2D [30]	✓	✓			spectrogram	100 Hz	0.5	8	88.8
FPbiLSTM [8]	✓	✓	✓		raw data	20 Hz	3.1	8	94.2
DT [33]	✓			✓	features	32 Hz / 1 sec	-	5	93.6
Fusion-MIL (ours)	✓			✓	spectrogram + raw data	10 Hz / 60 sec	0.6	8	92.6

TABLE IX
COMPARISON WITH LITERATURE

	No HMM		HMM	
	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score
<i>Per-placement</i>				
CNN1D [18]	55.3 ± 10.3	51.8 ± 12.6	63.3 ± 10.6	59.0 ± 14.0
CNN2D [30]	60.8 ± 6.9	59.5 ± 6.8	68.5 ± 7.2	65.0 ± 7.2
FPbiLSTM [8]	66.8 ± 4.8	65.0 ± 4.9	74.3 ± 6.4	70.0 ± 5.8
DT [33]	84.3 ± 1.2	72.5 ± 2.8	87.9 ± 1.6	79.6 ± 2.5
Fusion-MIL (ours)	85.1 ± 2.7	81.5 ± 2.4	89.1 ± 1.7	84.6 ± 2.4
<i>All-placements</i>				
CNN1D [18]	61.3 ± 8.7	58.8 ± 9.8	74.0 ± 9.0	72.5 ± 10.8
CNN2D [30]	67.5 ± 5.9	67.5 ± 5.0	76.3 ± 5.9	75.0 ± 5.3
FPbiLSTM [8]	75.5 ± 5.2	74.0 ± 3.7	84.3 ± 4.6	81.8 ± 3.3
DT [33]	85.9 ± 1.2	76.7 ± 2.1	90.1 ± 1.2	84.3 ± 2.5
Fusion-MIL (ours)	88.1 ± 2.4	86.7 ± 2.1	92.6 ± 1.7	90.8 ± 1.4

reveal very similar accuracy to what is reported in their paper, a notable deviation in the F1-Score is observed, likely due to considerable class imbalance in the SHL preview dataset, accentuated when combining all vehicles into a single category for the 5-class task.

Liang et al. [18] use a lightweight CNN model to recognize 7 TMs and achieve accuracy of 61.3% and F1-Score of 58.8%. They rely solely on acceleration signals, sampled at 50 Hz and segmented into 10-second windows. However, it is evident that their method exhibits a significantly lower performance compared to their reported results. This discrepancy can be attributed to their practice of using the same participant group for both training and testing phases. Specifically, they partitioned the dataset into 80% for training and 20% for testing which most probably influences the reported outcomes.

Ito et al.'s work [30] uses FFT spectrograms on 60-second windows acquired from acceleration and gyroscope signals data sampled at 100 Hz. They train a CNN model with synthesized images produced by arranging two spectrograms vertically and achieve accuracy of 67.5% and F1-Score of 67.5% in the all-placements experiment for the task of 8 TMs.

It is worth noting that [30] is the only other method of Tables VIII and IX that can operate with lower sampling-rate signals, as it relies on spectrograms. In our experiments, we have observed no significant loss of effectiveness for lower sampling rates. However, these effectiveness values are significantly lower than those reported in the original paper. This deviation can be ascribed to the nature of the dataset as it was exclusively collected by a single user and was considerably extensive, amounting to 271 hours in total with 95 hours designated for testing.

Tang et al. [8] use the same dataset [30], demonstrating

enhanced effectiveness through the integration of 3 distinct sensor types and the implementation a deep multimodal fusion network. Their approach combines data from accelerometers, magnetometers, and gyroscopes, each sampled at 20 Hz and segmented into 60-second windows. Introducing a feature pyramid network, which leverages both shallow-layer richness and deeper-layer feature resilience, their work achieves accuracy of 75.5% and F1-Score of 74% in the all-placements experiment for the task of 8 TMs.

Notably, there is a clear and consistent ranking in terms of recognition effectiveness among the various placements of the smartphone: Bag > Hips > Torso > Hand. Furthermore, all methods exhibit a substantial increase in effectiveness when trained across all different positions, as opposed to the per-placement experiment where only one position is used for training and testing. Finally, all methods seem to improve their effectiveness when incorporating the additional post-processing step (with HMMs).

From the results (Table IX), it can be seen that our method achieves better effectiveness in all settings and experiments, while using especially low sampling rates for both the accelerometer and location data.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have presented an approach to TMR using both acceleration and location signals. We lower the sampling rate requirements, since this plays a detrimental role in battery consumption. We proposed a model that extracts information from each modality separately and then embeds them in a common space in order to enable the use of an attention-based MIL approach. The final model is able to automatically use the most suitable modality for each transportation mode and even cope with missing data from a modality. We evaluate on a publicly available dataset and achieve high effectiveness (F1 score of 91%). We also evaluate on virtual scenarios where the position of the smartphone changes placement, and our model is able to maintain its robustness and even increase its effectiveness, obtaining an F1 score of 92.3%. Comparison with literature algorithms shows better results for our method overall.

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